

The day of the foundation of Vitry-le-François

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Here we show that the town of Vitry-le-François, a town created by Francis I of France in 1545, had been aligned with the rising sun on the day of the foundation.

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Vitry-le-François is a town in the Marne department in the north-eastern France. The old town was destroyed in 1142, when Louis VII invaded the Champagne and seized it. The present town was built, from 1545, at the behest of King Francis I of France, who wished to replace on a new site the town of Vitry-en-Perthois [1]. In fact, in 1544, Vitry-en-Perthois had been destroyed during the Italian War of 1542–46, a war that saw extensive fighting in Italy, France, and the Low Countries. The new Vitry was a modern city, built according to a plan given by Girolamo Marini [2]. The king's role in the creation of the new town resulted in the fact that we find his name as a part of the town's name. Moreover, the King of France gave also his emblem, the salamander, and his motto "Nutrisco et Extinguo" to the new city [1].

Despite some reluctance, a large part of the villagers of Vitry moved to Vitry-le-François, receiving economic benefits. The new Vitry was surrounded by walls and ramparts, with bastions protected by ditches (Fig.1). A citadel existed too, that was later destroyed. The fortifications were not completed until 1624.

Figure 1: Vitry in the Bing Maps.

We know the day of the foundation of the new Vitry-le-François.

On January 28, 1545, the King ordered the bailiff of Vitry to draw the plan and the ditches of the new town on the land of the Knights of St. John of Jerusalem [1].

Let us consider January 28. If we have to convert it from a Julian to a Gregorian date, we obtain February 7 (the Gregorian calendar was introduced in October 1582). We can use for the conversion one of the following links: www.galileo.fr.it/marc/varie/calendario/indice.htm or <http://www.dossier.net/utilities/calendar-converter/index.html>. Let us consider the direction of sunrise on February 7; using SunCalc.org software, a remarkable software which is giving sunrise and sunset directions on maps, we have that the planning of Vitry-le-François is aligned with the sunrise on this day (see the Figure 2). In the Figure 2, we see the orange line representing the sunrise direction on the astronomical horizon, whereas the yellow line corresponds to this direction on the natural horizon. And it is this direction which is perfectly corresponding to the axis of the town.

Figure 2: The town has two axes, one of them is aligned with the rising sun on February 7, which is corresponding to January 28 of the Julian calendar.

Therefore, in the case that the date of the foundation, the one that we find in Wikipedia [1], is given as a date of the Julian Calendar, we have that the layout of the new town had been aligned with the sunrise on the day of its foundation.

It is easy to find buildings, such as churches and cathedrals, aligned with the rising sun on the days of foundation ([3] and refs. therein), and it is also possible to observe the planning of ancient Roman towns, oriented towards the sunrise ([4] and refs. therein). Moreover, it is also possible to find some towns, founded in the Middle Ages, which are aligned with the rising sun [5]. Therefore, it is not surprising to find an alignment linked to the sunrise. What is remarkable, in the case of Vitry-le-François, it is the fact that we know the date of the foundation and that the axis of the town is perfectly matching the direction of sunrise on that day.

References

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